

A CONTENT ANALYSIS OF REVIEWS OF MODERN PHYSICS

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ABSTRACT:

This paper attempts to highlights the quantitative assessment of status of the Journal by way of analyzing the various features of Journal “the Reviews of Modern Physics”. During 2014-2018 a total of 204 Articles were published in the Journal “the Reviews of Modern Physics” by researchers in various countries.

KEYWORDS: Physics, Reviews of modern physics, Authorship Pattern, Collaboration

1. INTRODUCTION:

Content analysis is rapidly becoming less of a tool to be used in the experimental manipulation of the communication process. In these instances of experimental studies, systematic changes in content are made and documented through content analysis, and the audiences are observed for the effects of these changes.

The specific role to be played by content analysis in organizing for recall the world’s store of recorded knowledge. Content analysis appears to have two general and major functions. The first is to provide the descriptive abstract of any document at a level and of such a nature as will indicate what information may be found in it. The second is to provide guidelines in transforming document content from one medium to another and in reducing content for ease of bibliographic access.

Reviews of Modern Physics are a quarterly peer-reviewed scientific journal published by the American Physical Society. It was established in 1929 and the current editor-in-chief is Michael Thoennessen. The journal publishes review articles, usually by established researchers, on all aspects of physics and related fields. The reviews are usually accessible to non-specialists and serve as introductory material to graduate students, which survey recent work, discuss key problems to be solved and provide perspectives toward the end.

Reviews of Modern Physics are a Physics and Physics Journal and published by American Physical Society. See also a list of physics and physics journals.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The main objective of the study is to analyze the content of Journal of “Reviews of Modern Physics” and make the quantitative assessment of status of the Journal by way of analyzing the following features of Journal

1. To find out year-wise growth of publications,
2. To find out Geographical distribution of research output,
3. To find out the authorship and collaboration pattern in the publication,
4. To find out the most productive authors in the field,
5. To find out organization – wise distribution of publication,
6. To find out the channels of communications used by the scientists,
7. To find out the Annual Growth Rate Wise distributionand
8. To find out the Productivity Index.

3. SCOPE & LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

Scope of study is restricted to the “Reviews of Modern Physics” published during 2014 to 2018. The papers presented in the Journal are analyzed using content analysis technique.

The present study is limited to the total numbers of 204 papers published during 2014 to 2018.

4. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

The study consists of following hypothesis:

1. Authorship trend is towards multiple authored papers.
2. USA is the high productive country.
3. Majority of the affiliated Institution are from USA.

5. ANALYSIS OF “REVIEWS OF MODERN PHYSICS”

In views of the objectives of the present study, analysis of —International Journal of “Reviews of Modern Physics” is presented further (Reviews of Modern Physics, 2014).

5.1. YEAR-WISE PUBLICATION PRODUCTIVITY AND COLLABORATION RATE

The word publication means the act of publishing .Productivity refers to measures of output from production processes, per unit of input. Collaboration is a recursive process Where two or more people or organizations work together toward an intersection of common goals

Table 5.1: Year-Wise Publication Productivity and Collaboration Rate

Year	Single Authored Publication	Multi Author Publication	Total No of Publication	Collaboration Rate
2014	8	33	41	0.80
2015	12	29	41	0.71
2016	8	41	49	0.84
2017	12	31	43	0.72
2018	2	28	30	0.93
Total	42	162	204	0.79

Figure 5.1: Year-Wise Publication Productivity and Collaboration Rate

It can be observed from Table No.5.1 & figure No. 5.1 that during 2014-2018 a total of 204 Articles were published in the Journal of Reviews of Modern Physics by researchers in various countries.

5.2 GEOGRAPHICAL DISTRIBUTION OF RESEARCH OUTPUT

Geographical distribution of research output means the article published from different countries. In political geography and international politics, a country is a political division of a geographical entity. Frequently, but not exclusively, a sovereign territory, the term is most commonly associated with the notions of both state and nation, and also with government.

Table 5.2: Country-Wise Distribution of Articles

Sr. No	Country	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1	USA	74	36.27	1
2	Germany	20	9.80	2
3	Japan	12	5.88	3
4	UK	12	5.88	3
5	France	9	4.41	4
6	Italy	8	3.92	5
7	Austria	7	3.43	6
8	Netherlands	6	2.94	7
9	Spain	6	2.94	7
10	Belgium	4	1.96	8

Figure 5.2: Country-Wise Distribution of Articles

It can be observed from Table No 5.2 and Figure No. 5.2 that, there were as many as 27 countries carrying out research and produced 204 articles. Table no.2 provides ranked List of countries contributing to this field, the number of publications of each country and their share in percentages is the top producing country with 74 publications (36.27) of the total output. **Therefore, the hypothesis, “USA is the high productive country” (Hypotheses No.2) is valid.** It can be stated that USA being the publishing country the output is more than other country.

DOMESTIC AND INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATIVE PROFILE OF MOST PRODUCTIVE COUNTRIES:

Domestic and international collaborative profile of most productive countries has been calculated using Domestic Collaborative Index (DCI) and International Collaborative Index (ICI). Both the indexes (DCI/ICI) can be derived by calculating proportional output of domestically/internationally co-authored papers. The methodology is similar to one suggested by Frame (1977) and elaborated by Schubert and Braun (1986) and applied by Garg and Padhi (2001).

$$DCI = \{(Di/Di0) / (Do/Doo)\} \times 100 \text{ where}$$

Di= No. of domestically co-authored papers for country i

Di0= Total contribution of country i

Do= No. of domestically co-authored papers from all the countries

Doo = Total contribution from all the countries

Similarly, $ICI = \{(Ii/Ii0) / (Io/Ioo)\} \times 100$ where

Ii= No. of internationally co-authored papers for country i

Ii0= Total contribution of country i

Io= No. of internationally co-authored papers from all the countries

Ioo= Total contribution from all the countries

DCI/ ICI = 100 implies the country’s collaborative effort corresponds to the world average, DCI/ICI > 100 reflects higher than average collaboration effort, and DCI/ICI < 100 reflects lower than average collaboration effort by that country.

Table no. 5.3 Domestic and International Collaborative Indexes of Most Productive Countries

Country	Output	Collaborative Output	locally collaborated	Internationally collaborated	DCI
USA	74	40	20	10	0.45
Germany	20	10	8	6	0.67
Japan	12	6	4	2	0.56
UK	12	8	6	2	0.84
France	9	5	3	2	0.56
Italy	8	4	2	1	0.42
Austria	7	3	2	2	0.48
Netherlands	6	2	2	1	0.56
Spain	6	4	2	1	0.56
Belgium	4	2	1	0	0.42
Total	158	84	50	27	0.53

Domestic and international collaborative profile of most productive countries has been calculated using DCI and ICI and presented in Table – 5.3. It is observed that USA tops the list with 74 (DCI = 0.45) number of domestic collaboration. Other countries having above average DCI (>0.45) are Germany, Japan, UK, France, Italy, Austria, Netherland, Spain, and Belgium. The reason for the higher value of DCI for the USA is mainly due to the highest number of affiliated institutions (0.67%) belongs to the USA.

5.4 AUTHORSHIP AND COLLABORATION TREND:

Gupta, D.K.(4) Authorship is an observable phenomenon reflecting the contemporary scholarly practices clearly showing the communication, productivity and collaborative patterns and influences among researchers even though their quantities and qualities are not well understood.

Collaboration in research is said to have taken place when 2 or more persons work together on a scientific problem of project and effort, both physical and intellectual.

Table 5.4: Authorship and Collaboration Trend

Year	Single Author	Number of Papers with Various Authors							Total Publication
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	More Than - 7	
2014	8	5	6	5	5	1	2	9	41
2015	12	9	7	4	3	0	2	4	41
2016	8	6	13	8	3	5	1	5	49

2017	12	7	8	10	3	0	0	3	43
2018	2	5	6	3	6	5	1	2	30
Total	42	32	40	30	20	11	6	23	204
%	20.59	15.69	19.61	14.71	9.80	5.39	2.94	11.27	100.00

Figure No.5.4: Authorship and Collaboration Trend

It can be observed from Table No.5.4 and Figure No.5.4 that, year-wise authorship and collaboration trend is given in table 4. Authorship trend is towards multiple-authored papers. Single authored papers accounted for 20.59 %. **Therefore, the hypothesis, "Authorship trend is towards multiple authored papers. (Hypothesis No.1) is valid.**

5.5 MOST PRODUCTIVE AUTHOR:

An author is defined both as "the person who originates or gives existence to anything" and as "one who sets forth written statements" in the Oxford English Dictionary.

Table No.5.5: Most Productive Author

Sr. No	Author	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1	Frances Hellman	20	2.73	1
2	Hassan Aref	20	2.73	1
3	R. Joel England	20	2.73	1
4	Anna L. Watts	18	2.46	2
5	R. J. deBoer	13	1.78	3
6	Christoph Bostedt	10	1.37	4

7	Nicolas Brunner	10	1.37	4
8	Stephane Courteau	10	1.37	4
9	T. Dietl	10	1.37	4
10	Nine Authors Publishing Papers (9 x 1)	9	1.23	5
11	Eight Authors Publishing Papers (8 x 2)	16	2.19	6
12	Seven Authors Publishing Papers (7 x 6)	42	5.74	7
13	Six Authors Publishing Papers(6 x 14)	84	11.48	8
14	Five Authors Publishing Papers (5 x 20)	100	13.66	9
15	Four Authors Publishing Papers (4 x 32)	128	17.49	10
16	Three Authors Publishing Papers (3 x 37)	111	15.16	8
17	Two Authors Publishing Papers (2 x 34)	68	9.29	11
18	One Authors Publishing Papers (1 x 43)	43	5.87	12
Total		732	100	

It can be observed from Table No. 5.5 that, the most productive authors are Frances Hellman, Hassan Aref and R. Joel England who had the highest number (20) of the publication. Anna L. Watts with 18 Publications each, R. J. deBoer Authors with 13 publications, Christoph Bostedt, Nicolas Brunner, Stephane Courteau, and T. Dietl Authors with 10 publications. Nine Authors with 9 publications. Eight authors with 16 Publication Seven Authors with 42 publication Six Author with 84 publication five Authors with 100 publication Four Authors with 128 publication Three Authors with 111 publications. Two Authors with 68 publications and 43 authors with single publication.

5.6 INSTITUTES WISE DISTRIBUTION OF ARTICLES PUBLISHED:

Institution is a society or organization for the promotion of science, education etc. (5) .An institute is a permanent organizational body created for a certain purpose. Often it is a research organization (research institution) created to do research on specific topics. An institute can also be a professional body. In some countries institutes can be part of a university or other institution of higher education, either as a group of departments or an autonomous educational institution without a classic full university status such as a University Institute.

Table 5.6: Institutes wise distribution of articles

Sr. No	Institutes	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1	University of Delaware, Newark, Delaware 19716, USA and Joint Quantum Institute, National Institute of Standards and Technology and the University of Maryland, College Park, Maryland 20742, USA	74	36.27	1
2	Physikalisches Institut, Universität Stuttgart, Pfaffenwaldring 57, 70569 Stuttgart,	20	9.8	2

	Germany and Max-Planck-Institut für Intelligente Systeme, Heisenbergstraße 3, 70569 Stuttgart, Germany			
3	Meijo University, 1-501 Shiogama-guchi, Tempaku-ku, Nagoya 468-8502 Japan, and Nagoya University Akasaki Research Center, Furo-cho, Chikusa-ku, Nagoya 464-8601 Japan	12	5.88	3
4	School of Physics and Astronomy, University of Birmingham, Birmingham B15 2TT, United Kingdom	12	5.88	3
5	Univ. Grenoble Alpes, INAC-SPINTEC, F-38000 Grenoble, France	9	4.41	4
6	INFN, Torino Section, Via P. Giuria 1, I-10125 Torino, Italy	8	3.92	5
7	Institute for Theoretical Physics, Vienna University of Technology, 1040 Vienna, Austria	7	3.43	6
8	Van Swinderen Institute for Particle Physics and Gravity, University of Groningen, Nijenborgh 4, 9747 AG Groningen, The Netherlands	6	2.94	7
9	Instituto Nacional de Ciberseguridad, Avenida Jose Aguado, 41, Edificio INCIBE 24005, León, Spain and EI Telecomunicación, Department of Signal Theory and Communications, University of Vigo, Campus Universitario Lagoas-Marcosende, E-36310 Vigo, Spain	6	2.94	7
10	Four Authors Publishing Papers (4 X 3)	12	1.96	8
11	Three Authors Publishing Papers (3 X 3)	9	1.96	8
12	Two Authors Publishing Papers (2 X 2)	4	1.96	8
18	One Authors Publishing Papers (1 X 9)	9	0.49	11
27	Not Available	16	7.84	12
Total		204	100	

It can be observed from Table No. 5.6 that, there were 204 organizations involved in research activity. The organizations that have contributed in the publication during 2014- 2018. University of Delaware, Newark, Delaware 19716, USA and Joint Quantum Institute, National Institute of Standards and Technology and the University of Maryland, College Park, Maryland 20742, USA topped the list with 74 publication, followed by Physikalisches Institute, Universität Stuttgart, Pfaffenwaldring 57, 70569 Stuttgart, Germany and Max-Planck Institut für Intelligente Systeme, Heisenbergstraße 3, 70569 Stuttgart, Germany second list with 20 institutions, Followed by Meijo University, 1-501 Shiogama-guchi, Tempaku-ku, Nagoya 468-8502 Japan, and Nagoya University Akasaki Research Center, Furo-cho, Chikusa-ku, Nagoya 464-8601 Japan and School of Physics and Astronomy, University of Birmingham, Birmingham B15 2TT, United Kingdom third and fourth rank list with 12 publications, Followed by Univ. Grenoble Alpes, INAC-SPINTEC, F-38000 Grenoble, France with 9 publications, followed by INFN, Torino Section, Via P. Giuria 1, I-10125 Torino, Italy with 8 publications, followed by Institute for Theoretical Physics, Vienna

University of Technology, 1040 Vienna, Austria followed by Van Swinderen Institute for Particle Physics and Gravity, University of Groningen, Nijenborgh 4, 9747 AG Groningen, The Netherlands And Instituto Nacional de Ciberseguridad, Avenida Jose´ Aguado, 41, Edificio INCIBE 24005, Leo´n, Spain and El Telecommunicacio´n, Department of Signal Theory and Communications, University of Vigo, Campus Universitario Lagoas-Marcosende, E-36310 Vigo, Spain with 6 publication each. Four institutions with 12 publications, three institutions with 9 publications, two institutions with 4 publications, and 9 institutions with Single publication. **Therefore the hypothesis “Majority of the affiliated institution are from USA (Hypothesis No.3) is valid”.**

5.7 DISTRIBUTION OF LITERATURE IN VARIOUS CHANNELS OF COMMUNICATION:

Channel, in communications, refers to the medium used to convey information from a sender (or transmitter) to a receiver. Researchers communicated their publication through variety of communication channels

Table 5.7: Channels of Communication

Sr. No	Channels of Communications	No. of Publication	Percentage
1	Article	193	94.61
2	Note Publisher’s	8	3.92
3	Editorial	3	1.47
Total		204	100

Figure No: 5.7 Channels of Communication

It can be observed from table no. 5.7 and Figure No.5.7 that, Researchers communicated their publication through variety of communication channels 94.61% of the Literature was published in Article, Followed by Publisher’s Note (3.92%) and followed by the Editorial (1.47%). The total content of Reviews of Modern Physics that is Article, Publisher’s Note and Editorial, etc. is analyzed.

5.8. ANNUAL GROWTH RATE WISE DISTRIBUTION:

Table no. 5.8. Annual Growth Rate Wise distribution

Sr. No.	Year	Vol .No	Frequency	Annual Growth rate
1	2014	86	41	
2	2015	87	41	1.000
3	2016	88	49	0.20
4	2017	89	43	-0.12
5	2018	90	30	-0.30

In this table 5.8. & figure no. 5.8 observed that the Annual growth rate AGR of 2015 is 1.000 followed by 2016 are 0.20. Followed by 2017 are -0.12 & in the year 2018 with -0.30 are indicated. & so on highest AGR in the year 2015 with 1.000 & lowest AGR in the year 2017 with -0.12

5.9 PRODUCTIVITY INDEX:

With regard to the Lotka's classical method to test the regularity in publication activity of authors as cited above, the index called Productivity Index (PI) (Garcia, 2005; Sevukan, 2007) had been applied to identify the level of productions in IS literature. The PI is the logarithm values of n publications for each author which helped to find out three classical levels i.e. occasional producers, intermediate producers and larger producers as under:

- a) $PI = 0$ (Producing only 1 article each) ->Least producers
- b) $0 < PI < 1$ (Producing 2 to 9 articles) ->medium producers
- c) $PI \geq 1$ (Producing 10 or more articles) -> Larger producers

Table No.5.9 Productivity Index

Productivity Index	No. of Authors	Authors (%)	No. of Articles	Articles (%)	Level of Producers
$PI=0$ (1 Article)	41	5.60	41	20.10	Least Producers
$0 < PI < 1$ (2-9 articles)	568	77.60	8	3.92	Medium Producers
$PI \geq 1$ (10 or more articles)	123	16.80	155	75.98	Large Producers
Total	732	100	204	100.00	

Productivity Index (PI): With regard to the above aspect of Lotka's law, the index called Productivity Index (PI) has been applied to identify the level of classification of authors. The PI is the logarithm of the values of n publications for each author. The PI at Table –5.9, reveals that Least producers (5.60% authors) who published only one paper each ($PI = 0$) contribute as much as 20.10% of total JRMP literature while medium producers (77.60% authors) who published 2 – 9 papers ($0 < PI < 1$) contribute rest (3.92%) of JRMP literature in the Presence of larger producing group (16.80%), (who published 10+ papers; $PI > = 1$). Contribute rest (75.98%).

6. CONCLUSION:

Reviews of Modern Physics (RMP) is the world's premier physics review journal and the most highly cited *Physical Review* publication. Written by leading international researchers, RMP's in-depth essays provide outstanding coverage of a topic and give context and background for current research trends. During 2014-2018 a total of 204 Articles were published in the Journal of Reviews of Modern Physics by researchers in various countries. There were as many as 27 countries carrying out research and produced 204 articles. Table no.2 provides ranked List of countries contributing to this field, the number of publications of each country and their share in percentages is the top producing country with 74 publications (36.27) of the total output. Authorship trend is towards multiple-authored papers. Single authored papers accounted for 20.59 %. The most productive authors are Frances Hellman, Hassan Aref and R. Joel England who had the highest number (20) of the publication. There were 204 organizations involved in research activity. Researchers communicated their publication through variety of communication channels, 94.61% of the Literature was published in Article followed by Publisher's Note, Editorial, etc. Annual growth rate AGR of 2015 is 1.000 followed by 2016 are 0.20. Followed by 2017 are - 0.12 & in the year 2018 with -0.30 are indicated. & so on highest AGR in the year 2015 with 1.000 & lowest AGR in the year 2017 with -0.12. The productivity index (PI). The PI reveals that 123 authors published 10 articles or more have $PI \geq 1$ and can be considered as large producers. A medium percentage (16.80%) of authors contributed 155 articles (78.98%). 568 authors published 2 – 9 articles have $0 < PI < 1$ on the other hand, 38 authors (5.60%) have produced just one article ($PI=0$), which gives a value for the transience index (percentage of publications corresponding to occasional authors) of 3.48%.

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